

Factors Affecting Employee Performance at Makassar City's Regional Secretariat

Musmulyadi¹, Syafruddin², Andi Lutfi³, Muhammad Kamal Zubair⁴, Haeruddin Hafid⁵, Erwin⁶

^{1,4}Institut Agama Islam Negeri (IAIN) of Pare-Pare, Indonesia

²Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Kesehatan (STIKES) Salewangang Maros, Indonesia

³Sekolah Tinggi Ilmu Ekonomi (STIE) Tri Dharma Nusantara, Indonesia

^{5,6}Universitas Sulawesi Barat, Majene, Indonesia

Email: musmulyadi@iainpare.ac.id

Abstract

This study aimed to find out the factors compensation, working conditions, promotion, education and training have an effect on employee performance at Regional Secretariat office of Makassar. This study uses primary data through data collection questionnaire to obtain a sample of 124 respondents, the research conducted in July until September 2016. Data were analyzed using SPSS. The results of this study showed that of the factors, which will affect the performance of the employee compensation, working conditions, promotion, education and training, which show significant influence on employee performance is variable working conditions and compensation.

Keywords: *Employee Performance, Compensation, Working Conditions, Promotion, Education and Training.*

INTRODUCTION

The era of globalization which is marked by very fast changes in various sectors, global competition, the shorter the life cycle of innovation in the field of technology, changes in culture, social politics and others, will have an impact on changes in the conditions of the work environment both internally and externally. This change, at the same time, has a significant impact on human resources.

Every organization, both government and non-government, is currently improving itself to improve the quality of its human resources, both through formal and non-formal education, as well as improving skills and providing motivation. This is intended to deal with increasingly competitive work dynamics and demands to provide an increase in work performance that satisfies the parties served.

In this case, Government of Makassar City fully realize that the employee welfare can be achieved and improved if the performance of the employee improved. Employee performance can increase if the factors that affect the improvement of the employee's work are considered seriously, carefully, consistently, and carried out on an ongoing basis.

Makassar City Government conducted several policies regarding giving motivation and employee development in order to improving employee performance, especially employees within the Makassar City Regional Secretariat. For the development of human resources within the Makassar City Regional Secretariat, every employee is given the opportunity to attend training or education to a higher level. This is considering the work activities within the Makassar City Regional Secretariat, which are always dynamically progressing according to advances in science and technology.

Work motivation is the encouragement of a person or employee to take an action, activity or work that is beneficial to himself and the organization. The work was done because there was a stimulus from outside him. This stimulus can be in the form of appreciation and recognition from other parties. Basically, the award and or recognition must be fun for everyone, especially the employees.

Work motivation within the Makassar City Regional Secretariat has been considered through the fulfillment of intrinsic and extrinsic needs. Intrinsic needs include recognition of employee success, giving job responsibilities to employees, rewarding employees who excel, providing fun jobs and providing opportunities for growth and development. Extrinsic needs include incentives/salaries received by employees, reciprocal relationships between employees and leaders, relationships between employees/staff, working conditions created by leaders, facilities that support employee work, and work safety.

It is realized that the dynamic conditions of work faced by employees at the Makassar City Regional Secretariat are currently experiencing various changes and paradigms that direct government organizations to continue to strengthen the quality of their employees in carrying out their main tasks and functions.

The performance of employees at the Makassar City Regional Secretariat currently has not shown optimal work performance. Therefore, the way taken by policy makers in Makassar City is to improve the education of employees who are still low, provide superior skills to employees whose skill levels are still limited, involve employees in various trainings in order to improve mastery of the field of work that is still considered low, and strive to increase work motivation for each employee.

Research by Ashar (2004) with the research title "analysis of factors that influence the performance of the Village Secretariat apparatus and its apparatus in Ujung Loe District, Bulukumba Regency" is used as a reference in this study, because the research conducted by Ashar (2004) has independent variables the same is performance. The researcher uses this research as a reference with one different dependent variable, namely changing the discipline variable to the human resource development variable. In addition, this research was conducted in a different place, namely the Makassar City Regional Secretariat.

Immanuel & Mas'ud, (2017) conducted a study entitled Analysis of the Effect of Organizational Culture and Work Motivation on Employee Performance (Study at the Regional Human Resources Development Agency of Central Java Province) with research results showing that work motivation has a positive effect on employee performance. The results of this study are inversely proportional to the research conducted by Khazanah et al. (2019) with research results showing that motivation has a negative effect on employee performance.

From the description of the background and the problems that occur, the authors are interested in taking this theme further by choosing the title: "Factors Influencing Employee Performance at the Regional Secretariat of Makassar City" This study aims to find the effect of motivation and the influence of HR through compensation, workplace conditions, and promotions on the performance of the Makassar City Regional Secretariat employees and to determine the variables that most influence the performance of Makassar City Regional Secretariat employees. The benefits of this research as input for various parties, especially for policy making at the Makassar City Regional Secretariat related to providing motivation that can encourage morale and employee development in order to improve employee and organizational performance and can contribute to the field of management science, especially in the field of management human resources and provide additional information to researchers in the field of human resource management and as a policy for further research.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Definition of Human Sources Management

Human resource management in carrying out its functions will distribute workers to various fields within the organization according to their needs. This shows that human resource management has links with management in other areas of the organization to achieve effective work results. Of course, other fields will require quality work to maintain or improve their services to the community (Wilson, 2012).

Human resource management is inseparable from the understanding of the organization and individual human resources as workers who play an important role in the management of human resource organizations. Human resource management is essentially a series of activity processes in designing, planning, organizing, managing, and controlling individual resources so that they are proactive in planning, implementing, evaluating and reporting all their activities in accordance with the dynamics of work to achieve organizational goals (Nirmwan, 2004:169).

Education in an organization is a process of developing intellectual and personal abilities in the direction expected by the organization concerned. The basic concept of education has been found by experts including Redja Mulyahardjo (2001:11) who argues that education is a conscious effort carried out by families, communities, and the government, through guidance, teaching, and training activities, which take place at school and outside of school throughout life, to prepare students to be able to play roles in various roles in various environments appropriately in the future.

Training is a process of improving employee work skills to help achieve organizational or company goals. Initially, employee training was intended only for operational personnel, in order to have technical skills. But now training is given to every employee in the company, including administrative and managerial employees. Management is now together with employees to identify strategic goals and objectives in achieving the goals of the company or organization. Company managers or organizational leaders realize how important training is to increase job satisfaction (Wilson Wake 2012:202).

Thus, education and training is one of the most important factors in the development of human resources. Education and training not only increase knowledge but also increase work skills so that they can improve employee performance.

Definition of Motivation

Motivation comes from the Latin word "Movere" which means the drive or driving force of this motivation is only given to humans, especially to subordinates or followers (Hasibuan, 2001). Motivation questions how to encourage the passion of subordinates, so that they are willing to work hard by giving all their abilities and skills to realize company goals. Mathis & Jackson 2006 says, motivation is a desire in a person to cause that person to take an action. A person takes action for something to achieve a goal. Therefore, motivation is a driving force that leads to goals and it rarely appears in vain.

In this study will examine and deepen understanding of the process of work motivation related to work behavior (work behavior) work behavior in organizations will turn into initiatives and as directors in encouraging completing one's tasks and ending with performance (performance) if someone gets recognition (recognition), given responsibilities (responsibilities), achievements (achievements) are rewarded, if the job itself is fun and there is an opportunity to grow and develop (growth and development). (Intrinsic factors) which are job content.

Compensation is one of the important factors and is a concern for many organizations in retaining and attracting quality human resources, various organizations are competent to obtain quality human resources, because the quality of work results is determined by the competence possessed by their human resources, this reason makes many the organization spends a relatively large amount of money to develop its human resources so that they are compensated according to their needs.

In maintaining and increasing the productivity of a company, the role of human resource management is very important in terms of trying to make the workforce willing and able to provide the best possible work performance. In this case, the company is obliged to pay attention to the needs of its employees, both material and non-material.

With the opportunity for employees to be promoted, it will encourage the development of work dynamics that lead to increased employee performance and ultimately can improve the performance of the organization or company. Thus, the progress of an organization as measured by employee performance can be influenced by the provision of promotions.

Employee Performance

Performance (performance) is defined as an achievement of certain job requirements which ultimately can be clearly reflected in the resulting output (Simamora 2001:327).

Performance is a condition that must be known and informed to certain parties to determine the level of achievement of an organization's results that are related to the vision and mission carried out by an organization and to know the positive and negative impacts of predetermined operational policies. Performance is used by management to conduct periodic assessments of the operational effectiveness of an organization, the effectiveness of employees based on their main duties and functions (TUPOKSI) and based on predetermined standards. Performance (performance) both individuals and organizations can be used as a means of controlling (controlling) on the success of the organization.

Previous Research

A. Firma (2003) with the title: analysis of factors that influence the performance of high school teachers in Ujung Loe District, Bulukumba Regency. The results of this study indicate that there is a significant influence of motivation, cooperation, responsibility and leadership factors on improving teacher performance. The dominant factor influencing is work motivation.

Ashar (2004) with the research title: analysis of factors that influence the performance of the Village Secretariat apparatus and its apparatus in Ujung Loe District, Bulukumba Regency. The results of this study indicate that work discipline, work motivation and compensation have a significant effect on the performance of the apparatus. The dominant factor is work discipline and it is recommended that the sub-district always evaluates and develops its apparatus resources by analyzing various factors of human resource performance.

Hasanuddin (2005) with the research title: "analysis of factors that affect the performance of operational employees of Makassar advanced air traffic system Makassar Hasanuddin Airport. The results showed that leadership, motivation and communication had a significant effect on employee performance.

The results of the research above will be used as a reference or comparison material, in order to create relevant human resource management concepts and knowledge of organizational behavior and organizational culture as a basis in efforts to develop employee competence, so that organizational goals can be achieved.

METHOD

This study aims to empirically examine the regional secretariat of Makassar. Based on this explanation, this research is a quantitative research. This research plan will be conducted at the Makassar City Regional Secretariat office. Meanwhile, the time used for data collection and thesis preparation is estimated to be approximately three months starting from April to June 2020. The types of data used in this discussion are as Quantitative Data. While the sources of data needed in this study, sourced from primary data and secondary data. To obtain the data needed in order to carry out an analysis of the provisional answer or hypothesis of the problems raised in this study, the researchers used data collection techniques in the following ways, Observation, Interviews, Questionnaires, and Documentation. In carrying out their daily tasks, the Makassar City Regional Secretariat is supported by 600 (six hundred) civil servants and honorary employees. Given that the population is quite large, the Slovin theory according to Umar (2011:146) is used so that obtained 240 respondent. After the data were collected and processed, the next process is test the hypothesis or temporary answer using the following analysis method: 1) Validity and reliability test, 2) Multiple Regression Analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondent Characteristics

Based on the results of the study by taking a sample of 124 employees at the Regional Secretariat of Makassar City. Obtained an overview of the sample based on gender, age of the respondent, and the period of service of the respondent which can be described as follows:

1. Gender

Gender identity is used to understand and predict employees' attitude and behavior in responding and conducting their main tasks and functions. Based on the research results, in table 2 can explain that respondent characteristics at Makassar City Secretariat Office based on respondent's gender from 124 respondents (60,4%) is male and 49 respondents (39,6%) is female.

2. Based on the Age of the respondents

From all of the employees who become respondents, namely 124 employees, respondents who below 25 years old is 17 people or (13.71%), respondents who age is 25 years old is 52 people or (41.94%), respondents who are 35-40 years old is 36 people or (29.03%) while respondents who are 41-58 years old is 19 people or (15.32%). From the results of the study, when viewed from the age level of the respondents, it can be seen that 124 respondents were mostly respondents aged between 25 to 40 years. Table 3 shows that some of the respondents are in the young and productive category.

3. Based on The Respondent's Tenure

The respondent's tenure is the length of time an employee has been appointed as an employee. The lowest tenure is less than 10 years, while the highest employee tenure is more than 20 years. Table 4 showed that 35 respondents (28.23%) the working period is below 10 years, 68 respondents (54.84%) the working period is 10-20 years, and the employees who the working period is more than 20 years is 20 people or (16.93%).

Research Variables Description

Based on the main problem and hypothesis proposed in this research, there is independent variable consists of compensation, workplace condition, promotion, education and training. While dependent variable are employee performance, information or data descriptically obtained answers through questionnaire helped by the results of the interviews, it can be seen in the following description:

1. Performance Variable

Performance is a set of results obtained and pointed to achievement level as well as implementation in line with the work asked and the performance is a function of motivation and ability. The test result of primary data processing is:

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents on Employee Performance Variables

Indicators	5		4		3		2		1		Average
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Achievement	25	20,2	63	50,8	19	15,3	12	9,7	5	4,0	3,73
Respond	36	29,0	51	41,1	22	17,7	14	11,3	1	0,8	3,86
Work relationship	57	46,0	52	41,9	10	8,1	4	3,2	1	0,8	4,29
Pace	44	35,5	52	41,9	17	13,7	10	8,1	1	0,8	4,03
Discipline	46	37,1	58	46,8	12	9,7	7	5,6	1	0,8	4,14
Adapt	33	26,6	61	49,2	19	15,3	9	7,3	2	1,6	3,92

Source: Processed Data

Table 5 shows that the six employee performance indicators are regarding the achievements that have been achieved, responding to every complaint, being able to create working relationships, speed in completing work, discipline in carrying out tasks, and easy achievement. With an explanation of 5 (Strongly Agree), 4 (Agree), 3 (Quite Agree), 2 (Disagree), 1 (Strongly Disagree). The highest average response was 57 respondents or 46.0% stated strongly agree. This indicates that employees in the Makassar City Regional Secretariat have the ability to create good working relationships among employees and leaders. While the lowest response strongly agree is 25 respondents or 20.2% stated that employees have received recognition from others.

Based on table 5, 22 respondents or 17.7% express quiet agree that employees have the ability to respond to every complaint. While at least 10 respondent or (8.1%) express quite agree that the employees have the ability to respond to every complaint.

Responses strongly disagree on the indicators that employees have the ability to respond to every complaint, employees are able to create good working relationships, and employees are able to complete work and be disciplined in carrying out their functions and basically only 1 respondent or 0.8%. Meanwhile, 5 respondents disagreed or 4.0% stated that employees had received recognition from other people.

2. Compensation Variable

Compensation is something received by employees as the changes of their contribution services to corporation. Thus, compensation means not only in financial form, such as in the form of salary, wages, commission and bonus. The test results of primary data processing as follows:

Table 2. Distribution of Respondents Regarding Compensation Variable

Indicators	5		4		3		2		1		Average
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Salary	46	37,1	56	45,2	15	12,1	4	3,2	3	2,4	4,11
Additional	16	12,9	65	52,4	27	21,8	11	8,9	5	4,0	3,61
Vehicle	20	16,1	27	21,8	25	20,2	18	14,5	34	27,4	2,85
House	12	9,7	31	25,0	26	21,0	30	24,2	25	20,2	2,80
Allowance	32	25,8	39	31,5	20	16,1	20	16,1	13	10,5	3,46

Source: Processed Data

Table 6 shows that the five salary, allowance, incentive increases indicators pay attention to additional income improvement, vehicle and house ownership assistance as well as got health allowances. With the descriptions as 5 (very agree), 4 (agree), 3 (quite agree), 2 (Not agree), 1 (very not agree). The average of the highest respondents is 65 respondents or (54.2%) express that they are agree. It means that the respondents showed and pay attention to additional income improvement. While 27 respondents or 21.8% expressed they received vehicle ownership assistance.

In the salary, allowances and intensive increases indicators is extremely infect the employees work achievement are 46 respondents or 37.1% expressed they are extremely agree. While 12 respondents or 9.7% expressed that they received home ownership grant dana.

3. Workplace Condition Variable

Table 3. Distribution of Respondents Regarding Workplace Condition Variable

Indicators	5		4		3		2		1		Average
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Vehicle	41	33,1	40	32,3	25	20,2	10	8,1	8	6,5	3,77
Technology	50	40,3	47	37,9	18	14,5	7	5,6	2	1,6	4,10
Equipment	46	37,1	45	36,3	26	21,0	4	3,2	3	2,4	4,02
Cooler	61	49,2	47	37,9	11	8,9	5	4,0	-	-	4,32

Source: Processed Data

Table 7 shows that the four indicators are the availability of official vehicles, the availability of technological facilities, maintained equipment, maintained cooling or room fresheners. With an explanation of 5 (Strongly Agree), 4 (Agree), 3 (Quite Agree), 2 (Disagree), 1 (Strongly Disagree). The highest average response was 61 respondents or 49.2% stating strongly agree that the employees' work environment has been equipped with maintained air conditioners and air fresheners. While the responses of respondents strongly agree there are 41 people or 33.1% stating that at the workplace there are official vehicles available.

On the indicator that the workplace has available facilities and technology as well as refrigeration equipment, 47 respondents or 37.9% agreed. Meanwhile, 2 respondents or 1.6% stated that they strongly disagreed that the work

environment provided adequate technological facilities. Moreover, 8 respondents or 6.5% stated that they strongly disagreed with the availability of official vehicles.

4. Position Promotion Variable

Promotions are usually an employee transferred from one job to another with greater responsibility, a higher level in the hierarchy and a higher income. The test results from primary data management are as follows:

Table 4. Distribution of Respondents to Variables of Job Promotion

Indicators	5		4		3		2		1		Average
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Skills	16	12,9	55	44,4	22	17,7	13	10,5	18	14,5	3,31
Experiences	28	22,6	38	30,6	22	17,7	17	13,7	19	15,3	3,31
Disciplines	27	21,8	38	30,6	24	19,4	12	9,7	23	18,5	3,27
Loyalty	26	21,0	44	35,5	27	21,8	8	6,5	19	15,3	3,40
Rank	30	24,2	48	38,7	13	10,5	12	9,7	21	16,9	3,44

Source: Processed Data

Table 8 shows that the five indicators are in accordance with skills, work experience, work discipline, work loyalty, and based on rank. With an explanation of 5 (Strongly Agree), 4 (Agree), 3 (Quite Agree), 2 (Disagree), 1 (Strongly Disagree). The highest average response was 55 respondents or 44.4% agreed, meaning that it indicated that respondents agreed that the promotion was carried out according to the level of education and skills possessed by the employee. While the indicators of work experience possessed and the level of work discipline of employees as many as 38 respondents or 30.6% agreed.

19 respondents or 15.3% stated that they strongly disagreed if the promotion was carried out in accordance with the work experience that the employee had and based on the employee's work loyalty. While 23 respondents or 18.5% stated that they strongly disagreed if the promotion was carried out in accordance with the work experience possessed by the employee.

5. Education and Training Variables

Education and training is one of the most important factors in human resource development. Education and training not only increase knowledge but also increase work skills so that they can improve employee performance. The test results from primary data management are as follows:

Table 5. Distribution of Respondents on Education and Training Variables

Indicators	5		4		3		2		1		Average
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%	
Main functions	14	11,3	67	54,0	24	19,4	12	9,7	7	5,6	3,56
Necessity	20	16,1	56	45,2	29	23,4	14	11,3	5	4,0	3,58
Achievement	33	26,6	52	41,9	26	21,0	10	8,1	3	2,4	3,82
Understanding	33	26,6	54	43,5	28	22,6	7	5,6	2	1,6	3,88
Planning	25	20,2	57	46,0	25	20,2	12	9,7	5	4,0	3,69

Source: Processed data

Table 9 shows that the five indicators of education and training provided are in accordance with the main functions, needs, achievements, understanding, and planning. With an explanation of 5 (Strongly Agree), 4 (Agree), 3 (Quite Agree), 2 (Disagree), 1 (Strongly Disagree). The highest average response amounted to 67 respondents or 54.0% agreed, meaning that it indicates that respondents agree if the education and training of employees is in accordance with the duties and main functions of employees. While 33 respondents or 26.6% stated strongly agree that education and training can improve employee performance and can improve a good understanding. 2 respondents or 1.6% stated that they did not agree if the education and training taken could provide understanding.

Classical Assumption Deviation Test

The data obtained will be tested first through validity, reliability and normality analysis. This analysis aims to determine whether the data includes parametric or non-parametric tests. The primary data tested came from four independent variables, namely compensation, workplace conditions, promotions, education and training and one dependent variable, namely performance.

1. Validity Test

Validity test is used to determine whether the statement is feasible or not. An instrument is said to be valid if it is able to measure what it wants to measure and can reveal data on the variables studied on a regular basis. The decision criterion is that the instrument is said to be valid if it has a Pearson *product moment correlation coefficient* (r) $0.1484 >$ with α 0.05.

Table 6. The Result of Validity Test

Variables	Indicators	Items	Pearson Correlation	Product Moment Value	Information
				n=124, $\alpha=0,05$	
	Compensation	X1.1	0,352	0,1484	Valid
		X1.2	0,658	0,1484	Valid
		X1.3	0,847	0,1484	Valid
		X1.4	0,877	0,1484	Valid
		X1.5	0,800	0,1484	Valid
	Workplace Condition	X2.1	0,804	0,1484	Valid
		X2.2	0,852	0,1484	Valid
		X2.3	0,914	0,1484	Valid
		X2.4	0,760	0,1484	Valid
	Job promotion	X3.1	0,915	0,1484	Valid
		X3.2	0,951	0,1484	Valid
		X3.3	0,955	0,1484	Valid
		X3.4	0,930	0,1484	Valid
		X3.5	0,937	0,1484	Valid
	Education and Training	X4.1	0,847	0,1484	Valid
X4.2		0,902	0,1484	Valid	
X4.3		0,879	0,1484	Valid	
X4.4		0,833	0,1484	Valid	
X4.5		0,909	0,1484	Valid	
Employee Performance	Y1.1	0,806	0,1484	Valid	
	Y1.2	0,765	0,1484	Valid	
	Y1.3	0,768	0,1484	Valid	
	Y1.4	0,866	0,1484	Valid	
	Y1.5	0,745	0,1484	Valid	
	Y1.6	0,819	0,1484	Valid	

Source: Processed Data

Table 10 shows the results of the validity test of the compensation X1 variable, the value of person correlation (r count) is between 0.352 to 0.877, or r count $>$ r table 0.1484 meaning that each item of compensation variable statement used is valid.

The results of the validity test of the variable X2 workplace conditions, obtained the value of person correlation (r count) between 0.760 to 0.914, or r count $>$ r table 0.1484 which means that each item of the statement of the workplace condition variable used is valid. While the results of the validity test of the variable X3 for promotion, the value of person correlation (r count) is between 0.915 to 0.955, or r count $>$ r table 0.1484 meaning that each item of the statement of the promotion variable used is valid.

The result of the validity test of the variable X4 education and training, obtained person correlation value (r count) between 0.833 to 0.909, or r count $>$ r table 0.1484 is each item of the education and training variable statement used is valid. While the result of test validity of variable Y employees performance, obtained correlation person value (r count) between 0.745 to 0.866, or r count $>$ r table 0.1484 means each item of the employees performance variable used is valid.

2. Reliability Test

The research reliability instrument in this research tested used Coefficient cronbach's Alpha. An instrument said as reliable if it has reliability coefficient (α) 0.60 or more. Table 11 shows that reliability value used the same data on validity test, data test viewed as follows:

Table 7. The Result of Reliability Test

Variable	Indicators	Cronbach's Alpha	Information
	Compensation (X1)	0,774	Reliability
	Workplace condition (X2)	0,845	Reliability
	Job promotion (X3)	0,966	Reliability
	Education and training (X4)	0,923	Reliability
	Employee performance (Y1)	0,833	Reliability

Source: Processed Data

Table 7 shows that 100% of Cronbach's Alpha value is over 0.060 this test shows the measuring instrument used has met the requirements for parametric statistical tests.

3. Normality Test

Normality test is one of test in classic assumption. This test was conducted to see whether the regression model used had a normally distributed residual. A regression if the residuals are not normally distributed, it will result in an inconsistent and efficient regression.

The tests carried out in this study used the heteroscedasticity test and the normal plot which can be seen in the picture. The heteroscedasticity test in this study is intended to see whether the sampling is carried out correctly on the right population or in other words whether there is an inequality of variance from the regression residual. A regression model containing heteroscedasticity will produce biased parameters, which will cause errors in treatment. Every regression model is good if it does not obtain heteroscedasticity but homoscedasticity.

Heteroscedasticity test can be known by looking at the graph plot or the relationship between the dependent variable and the residual value. Heteroscedasticity will appear if there is a certain pattern between the two such as wavy and continuous or narrowing or widening regularly, while homoscedasticity will appear if there is no clear pattern or the points obtained spread above and below the number 0 or the Y axis. The results of the heteroscedasticity test of this study can be seen in Figure 2 below:

Figure 1. The Results of the Heteroscedasticity Test

Source: Processed Data

Based on the results of the classical assumption test, in this case the heteroscedasticity test shows that the points spread above and below the zero line randomly. This means that the regression model used in this study does not show heteroscedasticity, but homoscedasticity where this study does not produce bias parameters that cause errors in treatment.

Based on the display of the heteroscedasticity test above, it can be concluded that in Figure 2 shows homoscedasticity where this study does not produce bias parameters that cause errors in treatment. This shows that the regression model meets the assumption of normality, which can be seen in Figure 3 below:

Figure 2. Observed Cum Probability
Source: Processed Data

The normal probability plot display in Figure 3 above shows that the points are spread along the diagonal line, which means that the regression model used in this study has met the assumption of normality from the data so that the results will be good or according to the classical assumptions of a regression.

The Multiple Correlation Analysis (R)

The multiple correlation coefficients symbolized by R is used to measure the close relationship between the independent variables, compensation, workplace conditions, promotion, education and training. In addition, the dependent variable, employee performance. The greater the value of the correlation coefficient, the closer the relationship between the variables and vice versa.

According to Mendataris (2002:109) that to know correlation interpretation based on correlation coefficient obtained, then correlation-coefficient R value can be interpreted as follows:

1. Between 0,00 s/d 0.199: The relationship is very low
2. Between 0,20 s/d 0,399: The relationship is low
3. Between 0,40 s/d 0,599: The relationship is average
4. Between 0,60 s/d 0,799: The relationship is strong
5. Between 0,80 s/d 1,000: The relationship is very strong

Based on the calculation results obtained data as can be seen in the table below:

Table 8. Multiple Correlation Coefficient (R)

Model Summary					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.711 ^a	.506	.489	.52747	1.468

Predictors: (Constant), Job Promotion Education and Training, Workplace Conditions, Compensation
Dependent Variable: employee performance

Source: Processed Data

From table 12 above discovered that correlation analysis result obtained through SPSS program, all of independent variables are compensation, workplace condition, job promotion, education and training. In addition, the dependent variable is employee performance. This can be proven by looking at the multiple correlation coefficients (R) of 0.711. This shows that these four independent variables have a strong relationship to the dependent variable, because they are in the interval among 0.60 to 0.799.

1. Simultaneous t Test (F Test)

Table 9. ANOVE (F Test)

ANOVA ^a						
	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig
1	Regression	33.917	4	8.479	30.477	.000 ^b
	Residual	33.109	119	0.278		
	Total	67.026	123			

a. Dependent Variable: The average of employee's performance

b. The average of education and training, The average of Job promotion, The average of workplace condition, The average of Compensation

Source: Processed

From Table 13 shows that the calculated F value is 30,477, this shows that the calculated F is 30,477 with a significance of 0.000. F table can be seen in the statistical table (in the attachment) at a significant level of 0.05.

df 1 (Number of variables – 1)

$$5 - 1 = 4$$

$$df 2 = n - k - 1$$

$$= 124 - 4 - 1$$

$$= 119$$

Inf:

n: amount of data

k: number of dependent variables

The results obtained for the F table are 2.45.

From these results it is clear that the calculated F is greater than the F table ($30,477 > 2,45$) and significantly less than 0.05, namely $0.000 < 0.05$. This explains that the independent variable has a simultaneous relationship/influence on the dependent variable. Thus, the hypothesis is put forward that compensation, workplace conditions, promotions, education and training, stimulants or jointly affect the performance of employees at the Makassar City Regional Secretariat office.

2. Partial Test (t Test)

Partial hypothesis testing was carried out to determine the effect given by each independent variable on the dependent variable individually and to see the independent variable, which had a dominant influence on the dependent variable. This is done under the following conditions:

Formulating the Hypothesis

Ho: compensation variables, workplace conditions, promotions, education and training, stimulants or together have no effect on employee performance at the Makassar City Regional Secretariat office.

Ha: compensation variables, workplace conditions, promotions, education and training, stimulants or together have an effect on employee performance at the Makassar City Regional Secretariat Office Test Criteria

Test criteria:

- If t count < t table, then Ho is accepted

- If t count > t table, then Ho is rejected

From the results of the calculation analysis, the results of the analysis are as follows:

Table 10. T-Test

	Coefficients ^a			t	Sig
	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
	B	Std Error	Beta		
(Constant	1.259	.256		4.910	.000
Compensation	.261	.080	.308	3.254	.001
Workplace condition	.323	.079	.357	4.082	.000
Job Promotion	-.132	.051	-.226	-2.585	.011
Education & Training	.267	.074	.315	3.613	.000

Source: Processed Data

From Table 10 shows that the t count obtained against the t table. The value of the t table can be seen in the statistical table with a significant 0.05 with degrees of freedom $df = n - k - 1$ or $24 - 4 - 1 = 119$. The results obtained are 1.657.

1. Compensation
Based on table 14. The calculation results show that, the compensation variable (X1), has a significant value of 0.001 then $(0.001 < 0.005)$, with a t-count value of 3.254, which means $(3.254 > 1.657)$ Ho is rejected, indicating that the variable compensation significantly affects employee performance.
2. Workplace Condition
Based on Table 14, the calculation results show that the variable workplace conditions (X2), has a significant value of 0.000 then $(0.000 < 0.005)$, with a t-count value of 4.082 which means $(4.082 > 1.657)$ Ho is rejected, indicating that the variable of workplace conditions work significantly affects employee performance.
3. Job Promotion
Based on Table 14, the calculation results show that the promotion variable (X3), has a significant value of 0.011 then $(0.011 > 0.005)$, with the t-count value is -2.585, which means $(-2.585 < 1.657)$ Ho is accepted, indicating that the promotion variable position has no significant effect on employee performance.
4. Education and Training
Based on table 14, the calculation results shows that the education and training variable (X4) has significant value 0,000 then $0,000 < 0,005$, with t count value is 3,613, which means $(3,613 > 1,657)$ Ho is rejected, indicating the education and training variable significantly effecting employee performance.

From the information above, it can be seen that the independent variables that have t count greater than t table, namely compensation (X1), workplace conditions (X2), and education and training (X4) have a positive influence/relationship on the dependent variable, namely performance employee.

Based on Table 14, it is found that the multiple regression equation is as follows: $Y = 1,259 + 0,261 X1 + 0,323 X2 - 0,132 X3 + 0,267$. Based on the multiple linear regression equation obtained from the results of the SPSS program, there are positive results and negative results so that it can be seen that the influence of the independent variables (X) on the dependent variable (Y) can be interpreted Value $a = 1.259$ as a constant value obtained from the independent variable (X) to the dependent variable (Y).

The regression coefficient value of the compensation variable (b1) is positive, which is 0.261 indicating that the employee's performance will be positive if the compensation variable continues to be improved. The regression coefficient value of the workplace condition variable (b2) is positive, which is 0.323 indicating that if the workplace conditions are improved, the employee's performance will increase. The regression coefficient value of the education and training variable (b4) is positive, which is 0.267 indicating that the employee's performance will increase if the education and training variable is increased. This means that if the independent variables are increased such as compensation variables, workplace conditions, education and training which have positive values, they will increase the dependent variable, namely employee performance.

DISCUSSION

The discussion in this chapter attempts to answer the problems that have been formulated. Variables of compensation, workplace conditions, promotions, education and training that can affect employee performance in this study were tested or analyzed using multiple regression methods. Based on the results of the tests and analyzes carried out, it can be seen the magnitude of the regression coefficient and the significant level that can affect the variables analyzed.

Based on the purpose of this study, namely to determine the effect of compensation variables, workplace conditions, promotions, education and training have an effect on employee performance. The discussion regarding this will be described as follows:

1. Compensation

The results of hypothesis testing with regression analysis in table 14 show that motivation through compensation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. The results of this research test mean that motivation through the provision of compensation in the Makassar City Regional Secretariat office can improve employee performance. This is due to the existence of policies regarding salary increases, benefits and incentives, additional income improvements, home vehicle ownership assistance and family health benefits. Thus, giving satisfaction to employees so that they are always motivated to continue to carry out their main tasks well.

According to Sulistiyani & Rasidah (2003:206), the definition of compensation is everything that is received by employees as remuneration for their work, or in other words compensation is a contribution received by employees for the work that has been done.

2. Workplace Condition

The test results with regression analysis in table 14 show that motivation through workplace conditions has a positive and significant effect on employee performance within the Makassar City Regional Secretariat office. The more conducive the workplace conditions, the higher the performance that will be achieved by employees in the Makassar City Regional Secretariat office.

The results of this study are in line with the opinion of Habibi Asis (2007:85) which says that conducive workplace conditions will strengthen the role of human resources, especially in creating the performance of an organization. This is because in the employee's work environment there are adequate technology official vehicles, administrative equipment, and the availability of air conditioners and room fresheners.

Jack (2003:69) to enjoy work activities properly, it is necessary to have certainty and guarantee for a conducive workplace in carrying out daily work activities. The concrete form of the working environment conditions is a sense of calm and at home to work which is determined by the availability of work tools and equipment, a conducive working atmosphere and harmony between employees.

3. Job Promotion

Promotion is an employee award at a higher position than the previous position, with a higher level of responsibility as well. On the other hand, promotion is one of the efforts to develop employee performance. The results of this test indicate that promotion has no significant effect on employee performance in the Makassar City Regional Secretariat office. This shows that the higher the position of the employee, the lower the employee's performance, this can be seen from the results of research which show a negative coefficient value.

Based on the results of the study, the educational background and work experience of employees do not significantly affect the promotion of positions, but promotions and placements in a field are based on consideration of their seniority in rank. To increase organizational productivity, it is necessary to pay attention to human resource management, carry out objective, fair and appropriate position promotions and provide encouragement by the organization to employees so that the promotions carried out can provide encouragement to employees.

The results of this study are not supported by the results of research conducted by Habibi (2007) which says that the promotions carried out have a significant effect on employee performance.

4. Education and Training

Education in an organization is a process of developing intellectual and personal abilities in the direction expected by the organization concerned. Theoretically, it shows that the level of education of employees in an organization is positively related to the performance achieved by the employees concerned.

Conceptually it can be explained that the provision of training to employees in an organization is intended to improve the skills and work abilities of a person or group of people who are already working in an organization to increase productivity or performance to be achieved. With the training, there will be a process to assist the workforce in forming, improving and changing their knowledge, skills, attitudes and behavior in order to achieve certain standards according to what is required by their position. The test results with regression analysis in table 14 show that motivation through education and training has a positive and significant effect on employee performance within the Makassar City Regional Secretariat office.

This research is expected to be able to contribute to the leadership of the regional secretariat agency Makassar regarding the importance of providing motivation to employees because it can greatly affect employee performance. In addition, the development of human resources also has an influence on employee performance, with the development of human resources, of course, it will further increase employee skills so that it will produce good performance for the organization. This research is also expected to be a reference for further research so that further researchers can use other dependent variables that can affect employee performance.

CONCLUSION

The provision of compensation as a variable has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees in the Makassar City Secretariat office. This is due to the existence of policies regarding salary increases, benefits and incentives, additional income improvements, home vehicle ownership assistance and family health benefits.

Workplace conditions have a positive and significant effect on employee performance in the Makassar City Secretariat office. This is due to the availability of official vehicles, adequate technology, administrative equipment, and the availability of air conditioners and room fresheners.

Promotion does not have a positive effect on employee performance in the Makassar City Regional Secretariat office. This shows that promotion is not the most influential factor on employee performance. Education and training have a positive and significant effect on employee performance within the Makassar City Regional Secretariat office. This shows that with education and training, there will be a process to assist the workforce in forming, improving and changing their knowledge, skills, attitudes and behavior.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Anonim, (1999). *Guidelines for Preparation of Government Agencies Performance Accountability Report*. Jakarta: LAN RI.
- [2]. Bangun, W. (2012). *Human Resource Management*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- [3]. Barry, C. (2003). *Human Resource Management*. Jakarta: Elex Media Komputindo.
- [4]. Gomes, F. C. (2001). *Human Resource Management*. Yogyakarta: Andi Offset.
- [5]. Hasibuan, M. S. P. (2001). *Human Resource Management*. Yogyakarta: BPFE-UGM.
- [6]. Hasibuan, M. S. P. (2000). *Human Resource Management*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
- [7]. Mangkunegara, A. A. A. P. (2003). *Human Resource Empowerment in the World of Work*. Bandung: Tarsito.
- [8]. Mangkuprawira, T. S. (2003). *Human Resource Management Strategis*. Jakarta: Ghalia Indonesia.
- [9]. Martoyo, S. (1998). *Human Resource Management*. Yogyakarta: BPFE.
- [10]. Mathis, R. L., & Jackson, J. H. (2004). *Human Resource Management*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat
- [11]. Notoatmodjo, S. (2017). *Human Resources Development*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- [12]. Robbins, S. P. (2000). *Organizational Behavior Concepts, Contraventions and Applications*. Jakarta: Perhalindo.
- [13]. Siagian, S. P. (1999). *Human Resources Management*. Jakarta: Bumi Aksara.
- [14]. Sigit, S. (2003). *Organizational behavior*. Yogyakarta: BPFE.